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THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY PROFESSION-A CONCEPTUAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

A woman is strong, worthy and perfect in all professions in the globe, such women's are lack in STEM (science, technology, engineering, mathematics). There may be many reasons such as: gender gap, stereotypes, work-family conflict, work stress, women empowerment, failure to communicate effectively, personality traits, self-doubt et.al. But women contribution to IT sector is significant. Every successful woman with vision, like a little girl with lot of dreams, now a days women are entering in to every field as well as every sector. This study mainly focus on role of women in technology and the reasons of their paucity and consequently maximising the talent and minimising the barriers. This study discusses the social and structural factors such as: social expectations, work-family conflict and informal networks structural factors. This study mainly focuses on women contribution in IT sector, challenges faced in terms of gender biasness wage payment and promotion to higher positions etc.

Key words: *STEM, women, IT industry, gender gap, stereotypes, technology, work stress, gender discrimination, work life balance, women empowerment.*

Introduction

Information technology is now a days' playing a vital role in India and it is generating 2.5 million direct employments. Many of the big corporations in the world deal with IT such as: Google, Apple, Microsoft and Face book etc, generate massive amount of revenues and jobs. In Indian IT sector developed in massive way. The major information technology hubs are: Bangalore, Hyderabad, Chennai, Mumbai, Delhi, Noida, Gurgaon, and Pune etc., contributing to technology sector for both employers and employees. Now days, IT sector is contributing significant portion to the country GDP.

As people aware IT employees are facing several challenges like severe stress. Men can handle to some extent but women are in very sick position to handle stress levels in technology profession. Few companies are paving a path for employees to reduce the stress such as: recreational activities, stress breaks, adventure travel, family day functions, work out programmes, green food stalls to encourage healthy eating habits etc. IT sector is facing several problems which reflect impact on employees. They are:

Challenges faced by IT sector

1. Improve customer service by listening to and meeting client's needs.
2. Develop creative ways to minimise stress, satisfy employee needs, and match corporate needs to employee goals.
3. Manage and tame the complexity beast.

4. Increase the productive life of systems, software, and equipment.
5. Hiring, marketing and PR experts.
6. Instil a culture of teamwork among international team members with diverse backgrounds and varying ethnicities.
7. Determine what data, if any, is susceptible to bit rot and transfer to new media before it becomes a problem. (<http://www.techrepublic.com/blog/10-things/10-challenges-facing-it/>).

Young women professionals in the workforce

In total work force of IT sector the women work force is high. According to one survey, there are 17.2 million young professionals in 2016, in different occupational groups. The IT sector stood in third place (according to U.S. Bureau of Labour Statistics (BLS)).

Table 1: The table showing the percent of information technology profession stand in 2017

S.NO	Occupation	Percent
1	Management	5%
2	Business and Financial Operations	6%
3	Computer and Mathematical Science	5%
4	Architecture and Engineering	5%
5	Life, Physical, and Social Science	1%
6	Community and Social Service	3%
7	Legal	6%
8	Education, Training, and Library	7%
9	Arts, Entertainment, Sports, and Media	8%
10	Healthcare Practitioner and Technical Occupations	3%

According to the above table the young women most likely work in arts, entertainment, sports, and media, and education professions. In India most of the young womens are like to work in IT sector.

Factors affecting women in IT profession:

1. Sexism in the technology industry and in education.
2. The perceptions of people who work in technology.
3. Cultural biases such as different jobs for men and women.
4. The fact that women at a young age show an interest in technology then stops once they reach middle school.
5. The culture of the technology industry
6. Women in technology around the world (Paul B Hanton, 2015).

Literature Review

Deloitte Global predicts that, by end of 2016 fewer than 25 percent of information technology (IT) jobs in developed countries will be held by women, i.e. women working in IT roles. In fields of study related to IT especially, computer science it is clearly observed that, there are clear problems with gender diversity in the educational sector. For example, according to one survey, only 18 percent of US university computer science (CS) graduates in 2013 were women. According to a 2014 study among UK firms, half of all companies hiring IT workers stated that, only one-in-twenty job applicants were women. In IT sector, there is gender discrimination. A US female web developer makes 79 cents to the dollar men make for the same job; and while female computer and information systems managers have a narrower gap of 87 cents to the dollar. In the US a

quarter of women with IT roles feel stalled in their careers. Women in IT roles are 45 percent more likely than men to leave in their first year, according to a 2014 US study. Although some of the numbers on gender diversity in IT may appear disappointing, there are also hopeful signs. At one leading US technology school, computer science is now the most popular degree for women. Women in tech roles in US companies was 24 percent in 2014, and 27 percent of IT managerial roles were held by women (Paul Lee and Duncan Stewart, 2016).

According to Xie and Shauman (2003), “the percentage of women in STEM labour force is disproportionately lower than their share in STEM bachelor’s degree completion. Researchers have proposed different explanations for women’s attrition from STEM fields at the transition from college to employment (Rosser & Taylor, 2009; Xie & Shauman, 2003)”. According to Didio (1996), girls are only steered to softer subjects such as liberal arts and literature and away from mathematics and sciences.

Women leave tech jobs and are less likely to enter because of isolation, hostile, Male-dominated work environments, lack of effective sponsors. These are the effective factors pushing women to leave STEM (science, technology, engineering and technology) jobs- 53% of women and 31% of men are identified in 2016. According to one study more women pursue science disciplines in India’s higher education institutions than engineering or technology subjects, nearly half (46.7%) of undergraduate science majors were women, compared to IT and computer majors (44%) and engineering and technology majors (28.1%) in 2014–2015. Maccoby and Jacklin (1974), in an extensive review of sex differences, conclude that, self-confidence is one achievement related characteristic that consistently differentiates the sexes.

Compared to men, women are rated less desirable for management positions, are extended fewer job offers, and receive lower salaries (cf. Bowman, Worthy, & Greyson, 1965; Cecil, Paul & Olins, 1973; Cohen & Bunker, 1975; Dipboye, Fromkin, & Wiback, 1975; Haefner, 1977; Rosen & Jerdee, 1974a, 1974b; Schein, 1973, 1975; Terborg & Ilgen, 1975; Ullrich & Holden,). “Most working women probably are not qualified for management positions.

This is not meant to suggest that, women lack potential for the job, but that “the cumulative effects of past discrimination have prevented women from gaining necessary skills and experience”. Goetz and Herman (Note 2) and Deaux (Note 3) found that, even when job level was controlled, women were in positions of less responsibility, power, and influence.” According to (Treiman & Terrell, 1975), women still lag in lower salaries than men. Managerial motivation was related to managerial performance for women. Miner (1965) found that “the motivation of women changed with training and experience in a manner similar to that observed for men”. According to Hymowitz & Schellhardt, (1986) women lack in executive ranks in corporate jobs today in the society.

Shuttleworth (1992), said that, majority of women employed in routine and specialist work, while men are engaged in analytical and managerial activities. “Trade journals and academic research alike have confirmed that women in IT fields are concentrated at the lower and middle levels and are under-represented at the higher levels (Frenkle, 1990; Myers, 1990; Marengi, 1992; Mulqueen, 1996).” According to McKinsey (2010), companies with a higher proportion of women in their executive committees have better financial performance. Finally, more role models of women in the IT sector will attract increased female talent into the workforce (Panteli, 2012). A woman has five ways to define concept of career the figure below explores the role of women’s concept of career clearly step by step such as:

Fig 1: The women's concept of career

The women empowerment is required in present scenario to the womens to get financial freedom. There are several factors affecting the women empowerment which are shown in the figure below, among those women schooling is having much importance.

Fig 2: Factors surrounding women empowerment determinants and dimensions

In the above figure, there are determinants and dimensions where determinants like demographic, economic, social, media exposure etc factors are focussed and dimensions like self esteem, control of resources, decision making and mobility are intervened in empowering the women.

Table 2: The table showing components identified by the previous researches on the role of women in IT sector:

Sl.No	Author	Variable	Remarks
Work Stress			
1	Christo and Pienaar (2006)	Occupational stress	Loss of job and security, sitting for long periods of time or heavy lifting, lack of safety, complexity of repetitiveness and lack of autonomy in the job.
2	(Chand and Sethi, 1997)	Occupational stress	The role ambiguity, role overload, role conflict and strenuous working conditions.
3	Dr.k.krishnamurthy, Mr.S.Prabhakaran	Work stress	They identified that, stress factors include work factors, organisational factors, personal factors, health factors, environment factors, psychological factors, emotional factors, impact factors.
Work life balance			
1	N.krishnareddy(et.al) (2010)	Work family conflict and family work conflict	Size of family, age of children, work hours, level of social support.
2	Mk.Ahuja(2002)	Career advancement	Informal networks, Mentoring, organisational and institutional structure.
3	J. Sudha, Dr. P. Karthikeyan(2012)	Work stress	Group cohesiveness, functional dependence, communication frequency, workaholic regardless of gender.
4	J. Sudha, Dr. P. Karthikeyan(2012)	Child care	Work and family balance such as Getting ahead at Work, Completing the task within time, Commuting to/from work, and Spending valuable time with family Caring children and elderly parents Doing chores at home.
Women Empowerment			
1	Hashemi and Schuler (1993)	women empowerment	1. Sense of Self and Vision of the Future; 2. Mobility and Visibility; 3. Economic Security; 4. Decision Making Power in the Household; 5. Participation in Non-Family Groups; 6. Interact Effectively in the Public Sphere.
2	Julia Wiklander(2010)	women empowerment	Mobility, voice, decision-making in the family, property rights and freedom from domestic abuse, education, health care.
3	Trommlerova et al., 2015)	women empowerment	education, age, economic activity, country of residence
Gender discrimination			
1	G.Balatchandirane (2007)	Gender Discrimination	Education and Economic development
2	Zahid Ali Channar et.al(2011)	Gender Discrimination	Satisfaction and motivation, commitment and enthusiasm and less stress of the employees.
3	The gender gap report on world economic forum 2014	Gender discrimination	Economic participation and opportunity, educational attainment, health and survival and political empowerment.

Objectives of the study

The aim of this research is to study the state of female employment, gender equality and the qualitative experience of being a working woman in one of the most important and rapidly growing economic sectors namely IT sector, in the country.

1. To study the role of women in the information technology profession.
2. To evaluate the variables influence the women contribution for the development of information technology sector.

Discussion

IT is viewed as an important segment for the economic growth, giving rise to millions of new jobs and opening a gateway for women and men. In 2016, the Microsoft Company reported that, women comprise 29.1 percent of its workforce, but only 16.6 percent work in technical positions and just 23 percent hold leadership roles. Twitter said, women fill 10 percent of its technical jobs, with 21 percent in leadership. Googlers account for 17 percent of the search giant's tech jobs, while only 21 percent manage others (Roger Cheng, 2016).

If it sees, the level of economic empowerment is attained by woman in 128 countries. India rated quite poorly at spot 115. In fact, research done by the Centre for Talent Innovation has found that, 55percent of female Indian employees routinely encounter severe bias in the workplace that they disengage from their work. The Indian IT-BPO industry continues to be one of the fastest growing sectors in the Indian economy. Further, it has rapidly become one of the most economically significant industries in India in terms of share of total export (Jadine Lannon 2013). NASSCOM estimates that, the sector will create 230,000 jobs in FY2012, increasing the number of individuals employed directly in India's IT-BPO industry to about 2.8 million individuals. The IT industry is estimated to indirectly employ another 8.9 million people.

The IT industry in India is such an important source of employment for young Indian professionals (the median age of IT-BPO employees in India was about 24 in 2011), because, an unprecedented amount of those young professionals are women (women made up 42% of India's college graduates in 2010, and that figure was expected to continue to rise), IT companies have the potential to become leading examples of women-friendly employers. However, according to Dataquest's Best Employer Survey 2012, the percentage of women employed in the IT industry in India has actually decreased from 26 percent in 2010 to 22 percent in 2012 (Jadine Lannon 2013).

Many of these companies promote gender equality in the workplace and women in senior positions of authority; if it sees the basic facts about the Board of Directors and executive management teams of the six Indian IT companies. the Indian software sphere continues to be almost entirely male-dominated. In this connection if it sees, TCS' annual report for the 2011-2012 fiscal year reports a 14 member Board of Directors with one female non-executive director. Infosys Ltd. has 15 Board members: six executive members, none of which are women; one male chairperson; and eight non-executive independent members, one of whom is a woman. Wipro's Board of Directors is made up of 12 men: one executive chairman, two executive directors, and nine independent directors. As for their executive management team, the website lists 24 executive leaders, two of whom are women. HCL's Board has nine members, two of whom are executive members. The other seven members are listed as being independent, non-executive members. One of these non-executive members is a woman. Tech Mahindra's Board of Directors sits a non-executive chairman, one executive member, six non-executive independent members, and three non-executive directors. None of these individuals are female. According to 2011-2012 annual report, Mahindra Satyam's Board of Directors boosts 6 members: a male chairman, one male CEO, and four non-executive board members, one of whom is an Indian woman (Jadine Lannon 2013). This percentage is not enough to women in board of directors in IT sector companies it should be increased. The companies should follow the government rules and try to avoid gender bias in work place and giving promotions.

There is a widespread recognition of the routine discrimination faced by Indian womens, in their private and professional life. Issues of female economic empowerment tend to get downplayed when juxtaposed against the entirety of the system of discrimination and violence faced by women in India. For women there are certain barriers in IT sector they are striving hard to overcome those barriers by taking remedial steps. The major barriers are:

1. Gender gaps in the education pipeline.
2. Bias in advertising of positions.
3. Bias in recruiting.
4. Retention of female staff.
5. A deemed glass ceiling in terms of promotions and pay.

All these biases should be avoided and importance to women must give for the improvement of overall organizational performance. There are few variables that influence the women contribution for the development of information technology sector such as: Work environment, effective job orientation, continuous pressure to achieve targets, infrastructure facilities, well organised duties and responsibilities, reasonable work load, favourable work atmosphere, availability of management to discuss job related issues, availability of sufficient resources, encouragement for open communication at workplace.

Source: https://www.ncwit.org/sites/default/files/resources/btn_03092016_web.pdf

Fig 3: Statistics showing women role in information technology profession by numbers

The above figure elucidated clearly, the latest statistics of women in information technology profession; firstly, 57 percentage of women are held in professional occupations. And 25 percentage of women occupied professional computing positions. Moreover, 17 percentage of women occupied fortune 500 chief information officer positions. Likewise, 59 percentage of (ISEF) Intel science and engineering fair finalists for biology categories of women and 25 percentage are mathematics and 23 percentage are computing categories of women.

Table 3: Latest statistics of women in technology profession

Type of Women Profession	Percent
Proprietary software jobs held by women	28%
IT jobs held by women	25%
Women executives at Fortune 500 companies	11%
Tech start-ups owned by women	5%

Source: <https://www.themuse.com/advice/the-latest-stats-on-women-in-tech>

The above table shows that, the latest statistics of the type of profession women has and its percentage such as, proprietary software jobs held by women are 28%,and 25% are IT jobs held by women and likewise 11% are women executives at fortune 500 company and 5% are tech start-ups owned by women.

Source: www.dol.gov/wb/stats/stats_data.htm

Fig 4: The participation of women in different fields including IT profession

As per the above figure, latest statistics of women in different fields are; 57% of women participate in the labour force, 26% of women employed in computer and mathematical operations, 70% of women are under 18 years participate in the labour force and 21.7% in wage gap likewise 78.3% in earnings ratio. The statistics of women are clearly focussed in the above figure in the information technology profession. (www.dol.gov/wb/stats/stats_data.htm)

As discussed, the fairly high profile of this issue, the trend for representation of women in IT over the last decade is actually slightly down, with current figures showing just 20 per cent in the industry as a whole. This

trend should be changed more importance should be given to women for the development of organizational efficiency.

Drilling down to specialist areas it gets worse: within the IT sector itself only 11 per cent of IT specialists were women and the median gross weekly rate of pay for female IT specialists was 16 per cent less than the comparison figure for men working in IT roles.

And mainly in IT sector the salary structure is spectacular even though there is a biasness and gender-gap in salaries for men and women. And promotions to higher level executive posts are mainly men; women are given less priority to promotions in higher managerial posts. Apart from this there are several other problems faced by the woman in IT sector, such as;

Fig 5: Problems faced by women in IT sector

This study mainly focuses on the problems faced by women in IT such as; work stress and health conditions, likewise self doubt, and failure to communicate effectively and personality traits and work family conflict are the major problems that affect the women in information technology profession.

Conclusion:

This study concludes by depicting the women problems like work stress, failure to communicate effectively and self doubt, which required more attention to address by the authorities. This study mainly suggests that, women have to be treated fairly and biasness in respect to salary structure and promotion to higher executive positions should be avoided. Proper measures have to be taken by IT sector for women employees such as; monitoring of working conditions, creation of industrial harmony through infrastructure for health, industrial relations and insurance against disease, accident and unemployment for the workers and their families are best welfare activities they can provide for their employees.

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